

TDC Tools: streamlining information retrieval applications thanks to a tabular Document-Concept representation of the biomedical literature

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August 2021

Abstract

Motivation: Several methods can be used to obtain the content of the biomedical literature articles annotated with standardized concepts. Various information retrieval (IR) applications exploit these resources, e.g. Literature-Based Discovery (LBD). Such applications often require a complex processing pipeline to transform the raw literature into an appropriate structured representation.

Results: TDC Tools offer an intermediate level of representation aimed to facilitate the design and implementation of IR systems exploiting a concept-based view of the literature. Conceptually this intermediate representation decouples the data extraction part from the task-specific exploitation part, thus improving the modularity, interoperability and ultimately the reusability of such systems.

Availability: The software and its dependencies are published under open-source license and provided with detailed instructions: <https://github.com/erwanm/tdc-tools>.¹

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1 Introduction

Nowadays virtually any biomedical research work is available almost instantly in digital form, but exploring the literature is made challenging by the ever-increasing amount of publications. In this context automated data mining methods offer an efficient way to explore the literature, and these may also pave the way for novel research methodologies. Literature-

Based Discovery (LBD) is such a promising research-oriented application [1]: LBD aims to help researchers to identify relations between concepts which are worthy of further investigation. Existing LBD methods rely on a structured representation (e.g. graph or vector space) of the relations between concepts as found in the literature in order to infer new candidate relations.

Existing LBD systems e.g. [2, 4] often encompass both the data extraction and data exploitation parts into an end-to-end system: they are fed with the biomedical literature in some predefined format as input and produce the inferred new relations as output. Various data sources and formats can be used as input [5]; even in the standard case where Medline² and PubMed Central (PMC)³ are used as the primary data source, various options exist for annotating and extracting the concepts.

In this paper we advocate for decoupling the data extraction and data exploitation parts as two separate tasks, in LBD as well as any other high-level application based on the relations between concepts in the literature. This design would allow authors of such systems to focus solely on the high-level task by relying on some state of the art system for the low-level data extraction part and conversely (modularity). This would also permit the combination of any data extraction method with any high-level method (interoperability), thus improving the reusability of the software and the reproducibility of the results. Moreover the data extraction part is very computer-intensive, thus the possibility to store the structured data in a standard format offers a major advantage in terms of usability and efficiency: for a given high-level application such as LBD, different methods can be tested against the same dataset.

¹The 2021 datasets are also available: <https://zenodo.org/record/5138386> (based on the data downloaded in January 2021).

²https://www.nlm.nih.gov/databases/download/pubmed_medline.html

³<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/tools/openftlist/>

Figure 1: The TDC processing pipeline is compatible with various data collection/extraction methods, offers standard data representation techniques and pre-computes (co-)occurrence statistics for flexible application usage.

This paper presents the TDC Tools library, which implements this principle through an intermediate representation of the data called the Tabular Document-Concept (TDC) format. The library is intended primarily as a proof of concept: two available data extraction methods are available while new methods can be added in the future.

2 Methods

2.1 Data sources

The traditional approach for mining biomedical concepts from the Medline abstracts and PubMedCentral (PMC) articles (used e.g. by [2]) requires parsing the raw data and string-matching concepts using a controlled vocabulary such as the UMLS meta-thesaurus.⁴ A modified version⁵ of the “Knowledge Discovery” code by [2] can be used to generate data in the TDC format. The extracted concepts are represented as UMLS Concept Uniques Identifiers (CUIs).

PubTator Central (PTC) provides all the Medline and PMC documents annotated with state-of-the-art text mining systems [6]. PTC greatly simplifies the literature mining process and has become the standard option for the data collection stage in LBD systems. However the PTC mining process is not error-free. For example it has been observed that mentions of the disease “frontotemporal dementia” are mistakenly identified as the more general disease of “dementia” [3]. TDC Tools contain a script which converts the PTC data to the TDC format.

⁴<https://www.nlm.nih.gov/research/umls/index.html>

⁵<https://github.com/erwanm/knowledgediscovery>. An additional step of disambiguation is necessary, it can be performed using the ad-hoc disambiguation system available at <https://github.com/erwanm/kd-data-tools>.

2.2 The TDC Format

The TDC format is made of three data tables: by document, by sentence and by concept mention. The mentions are referenced by their document and sentence ids, allowing the context in which a concept is mentioned to be retrieved. The data is organized by year of publication and split into two categories: PMC full articles vs. Medline abstracts.

The Document-Concept Matrix (DCM) can be computed from the TDC format. At this stage a *document* is represented as a (multi-)set of concepts (the full text is not represented anymore). A *document* is either a single sentence or a single paper (abstract or full article), permitting the collection of co-occurrence statistics at different levels: sentence-level co-occurrences denote a stronger relationship but paper-level co-occurrences cover a more diverse range of relationships.

The final stage of the TDC Tools pipeline extracts the frequency of individual concepts and/or concepts pairs, for every year and every view of the data (abstracts only, full articles only, or both; by sentence or by paper). The publication year is preserved, allowing a range of years to be selected for time-aware statistics. The use of raw frequency values offers optimal flexibility for further calculations involving probabilities. For example Pointwise Mutual Information can be obtained but also any other measure of association strength. Additionally the storage of integer values is optimal in terms of efficiency and precision, as opposed to storing probabilities.

The different formats are also suitable for efficient database storage and service through an API.

3 Conclusion

TDC tools offer a standardized and flexible way to obtain a concept-based representation of the biomedical literature. Downstream, the process is agnostic with respect to the data extraction method; upstream, the processed data can be exploited by many high-level IR applications, in particular LBD. In the future, the simplification of this computationally heavy process may give rise to novel fruitful applications.

Funding

This work was conducted with the financial support of Irish Health Research Board (HRB) BRAIN-Mend project (grant number HRB-JPI-JPND-2017-1) and with the support of the Science Foundation Ireland Research Centre ADAPT (grant number 13/RC/2106_P2).

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